

INTERACTION OF SULPHURYL CHLORIDE WITH ARYLAMIDES OF AROMATIC ACIDS. PART I.

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Sulphuryl chloride gives chlorinated products with arylamides of benzoic acid. Chlorine first enters the basic part of the molecule in position *para* to the amido group and with excess of sulphuryl chloride dichloro derivatives are formed, the second chlorine atom entering the same nucleus. The constitution of the compounds is proved by hydrolysis as well as by synthesis.

Sulphuryl chloride has been used as a chlorinating agent in the case of aromatic compounds with various substituents like OR, NR₂, COOH, etc. and it has been noted that its reactivity depends upon the substituents in the nucleus.

Although aromatic hydrocarbons give chloro derivatives, introduction of an anionoid group like NH₂, greatly increases the reactivity of the molecule (cf. Wenghöffer, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1877, ii, 16, 449). When, however, the basic character of the amine is neutralised by acylation, either a dichloro or a monochloro derivative is obtained as is shown by Wenghöffer (*loc. cit.*) and Wynne (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 61, 1042).

Benzarylamides are very reactive towards sulphuryl chloride and the reaction products cannot be isolated. Use of dry benzene is found convenient to control the vigour of the reaction. Action of sulphuryl chloride has been attempted on benzoyl derivatives of aniline, *o*- and *m*-chloro-anilines, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, *p*-anisidine, *p*-phenetidine, α - and β -naphthylamines, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroanilines and *o*-nitro-*p*-toluidine.

Benz-nitroarylamides, except benz-*o*-nitroanilide, failed to give reaction products due to the deactivating influence of the nitro group in the molecule.

The constitution of halogenated products is proved by (i) hydrolysis and identifying the chloroamine obtained or its acetyl derivative as well as the acid, by mixed melting point with an authentic specimen and (ii) by mixed melting point of the reaction product with benzoyl derivative of the chloroamine.

It has been observed that chlorine generally first enters the position *para* to the amido group whenever free and when excess of sulphuryl chloride is used, to *ortho* as is found in the case of anilide, *m*-toluidide, *o*-toluidide and α -naphthylamide.

It seems that the orienting influences of methoxy and amido groups are nearly equal because dichloro derivative of benz-*p*-anisidine can always be obtained under experimental conditions.

Although it is well known that *o*-*p*-directing influence of the amido group is more powerful than alkoxy group, benz-2-chloro-*p*-phenetidine (OC₂H₅ = 1) can be isolated, together with benz-2:5-dichloro-*p*-phenetidine in the chlorination of benz-*p*-phenetidine with sulphuryl chloride,

In the case of benz-*m*-toluidide, excess of sulphuryl chloride gave two chloro derivatives, one of which (m.p. 111-12°) has been proved to be benz-4:6-dichloro-*m*-toluidide (Me=1) both by hydrolysis to 4:6-dichloro-3-aminotoluene and by preparing it from 4:6-dichloro-3-aminotoluene by benzoylation. The other compound (m.p. 147-48°) is considered to be benz-2:6-dichloro-*m*-toluidide (Me=1) because the melting point of the corresponding acetyl derivative (m.p. 117°) agrees well with that described by Cohen and Dakin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 1331). Only other constitution possible for that compound is benz-5:6-dichloro-*m*-toluidide, but the melting point of the acetyl derivative of 5:6-dichloro-*m*-toluidine is 187°.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sulphuryl chloride was gradually added to the amide suspended in dry benzene (about 40 c.c. for 5 g. of amide) and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature being protected from moisture. As the reaction started, the amide dissolved in the solvent and the solution was then boiled under reflux for about 4 hours, except in the case of benz-*p*-anisidide (1:1) when it was boiled for 2 hours only. The reaction product, after removal of benzene, was washed free from sulphuryl chloride with dry petroleum. The substances were generally soluble in benzene, alcohol and acetic acid and were crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, except in the case of benz-*o*-nitroanilide when it was yellowish.

In the case of benz-*p*-toluidide and benz-*p*-phenetidide, where two products are simultaneously formed, they were separated by fractional crystallisation from alcohol.

Constitution of products marked (A) is proved by hydrolysis to the known amine and benzoylation of the corresponding amine.

Substances marked (B) are identified by hydrolysis to the corresponding amine only and those marked (C) by synthesis only. In the case of substances marked (D) in addition to (A) or (B), the amine was identified through its acetyl derivative (by mixed melting point with an authentic sample). Benz-2-nitro-4-chloroanilide was prepared by nitrating benz-*p*-chloroanilide with dilute nitric acid (1:1). In the case of chloro derivatives of benzanilide, benz-*o*-toluidide, benz-*m*-chloroanilide and monochloro derivative of benz-*m*-toluidide, hydrolysis was carried out by boiling the substances with 50% alcoholic caustic potash solution for about 6 hours. Remaining substances were hydrolysed by heating with 50% alcoholic caustic potash solution in a sealed tube at 160-70° for about 6 hours.

The following table shows the details of the substances.

TABLE I

Anide.	Proportion of amide to SO_2Cl_2 .	Product.	M.p.	Formula.	Found.	Analysis Required.	Yield.
Benzamide	1:1	Benz- <i>p</i> -chloroanilide (A&D)	190-91°	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONCl}$	Cl, 15.3%	Cl, 15.3%	90%
Benzanilide	1:2	Benz-2,4-dichloroanilide (A)	115-16°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{ONCl}_2$	Cl, 26.6	Cl, 26.7	80
Benz- <i>m</i> -chloroanilide	1:1	Benz-2,4-dichloroanilide*	115-16°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{ONCl}_2$	Cl, 26.5	Cl, 26.7	80
Benz- <i>m</i> -chloroanilide	1:1	Benz-2,4-dichloroanilide (A)	143-44°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{ONCl}_2$	Cl, 26.5	Cl, 26.7	75
Benz- <i>o</i> -toluidide	1:1	Benz-5-chloro- <i>o</i> -toluidide (A&D)	162-63°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONCl}$	Cl, 14.4	Cl, 14.5	90
Benz- <i>o</i> -toluidide	1:2	Benz-5-chloro- <i>o</i> -toluidide*	162-63°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONCl}$	—	—	—
Benz- <i>m</i> -toluidide	1:1	Benz-6-chloro- <i>m</i> -toluidide (A)	116-18°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONCl}$	Cl, 14.3	Cl, 14.5	—
Benz- <i>m</i> -toluidide	1:2	(f) Benz-2,6-dichloro- <i>m</i> -toluidide (P&D)	147-48°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONCl}_2$	Cl, 25.1	Cl, 25.3	20
Benz- <i>p</i> -toluidide	1:1	(f) Benz-2,6-dichloro- <i>m</i> -toluidide (A)	111-12°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONCl}_2$	Cl, 25.2 N, 5.1	Cl, 25.3 N, 5.0	70
Benz- <i>p</i> -toluidide	1:1	Benz-3-chloro- <i>p</i> -toluidide (A&D)	139°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONCl}$	Cl, 14.2	Cl, 14.5	—
Benz- <i>p</i> -toluidide	1:2	(f) Benz-3,5-dichloro- <i>p</i> -toluidide (A&D)	114-115°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONCl}_2$	Cl, 25.2	Cl, 25.3	—
Benz- <i>p</i> -toluidide	1:2	(f) Benz-3-chloro- <i>p</i> -toluidide*	138°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONCl}$	—	—	—

TABLE I (contd.).

Amide.	Proportion of amide to SO_2Cl_2 .	Product.	M.p.	Formula.	Found.	Analysis Required.	Yield.
Benz- <i>p</i> -anisidide	1:1	Benz-2:5-dichloro- <i>p</i> -anisidide*	136-37°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_2$	Cl, 23.7%	Cl, 23.9%	—
Benz- <i>p</i> -anisidide	1:2	Benz-2:5-dichloro- <i>p</i> -anisidide (C)	136-37°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_2$	Cl, 23.7	Cl, 23.9	70%
Benz- <i>p</i> -phenetidide	1:1	(f) Benz-2-chloro- <i>p</i> -phenetidide (C)	171-72°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$	Cl, 12.7	Cl, 12.9	20
Benz- <i>p</i> -phenetidide	1:2	(ff) Benz-2:5-dichloro- <i>p</i> -phenetidide (C)	143-44°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_2$	Cl, 22.7	Cl, 22.9	60
Benz- <i>p</i> -phenetidide	1:2	Benz-2:5-dichloro- <i>p</i> -phenetidide*	144-45°	—	—	—	—
Benz- α -naphthylamide	1:1	Benz- α -chloro- α -naphthylamide (A)	226°	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{ONCl}$	Cl, 12.7	Cl, 12.7	85
Benz- α -naphthylamide	1:2	Benz-2:4-dichloro- α -naphthylamide (A)	212-213°	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{ONCl}_2$	Cl, 22.3	Cl, 22.5	70
Benz- β -naphthylamide	1:1	Benz-1-chloro- β -naphthylamide (A)	171°	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{ONCl}$	Cl, 12.6	Cl, 12.7	80
Benz- α -nitroanilide	1:1	Benz- α -nitro- α -chloroanilide (D)	130°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$	Cl, 12.6 N, 10.1	Cl, 12.8 N, 10.2	

N.B.—(f) In the case of toluhides, anilidide and phenetidide Me, OMe, and OEt are numbered 1.

(ff) Substances marked* were identified by mixed m.p. with authentic specimens.

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